

Robust Aggregation Technique Against Poisoning Attacks in Multi-Stage Federated Learning Applications

Yushan Siriwardhana*, Pawani Porambage†, Madhusanka Liyanage‡, Samuel Marchal§, Mika Ylianttila¶,

*¶Centre for Wireless Communications, University of Oulu, Finland

†VTT Technical Research Centre, Finland

‡School of Computer Science, University College Dublin, Ireland

§WithSecure Corp. & Aalto University

Email: *¶[firstname.lastname]@oulu.fi, †pawani.porambage@vtt.fi, ‡madhusanka@ucd.ie,

§samuel.marchal@withsecure.com

Abstract—Federated Learning (FL) is a distributed Machine Learning (ML) technique that allows model training without sharing data. FL is vulnerable to poisoning attacks where an adversary manipulates the learning process by providing false information to the federation. Ensuring security in FL is vital before using FL in real applications, as the consequences can be adverse. Multi-stage FL is a novel variant of FL that performs intermediate model aggregations, thereby reducing the traffic toward the FL central server. The existing robust aggregation techniques are insufficient in multi-stage FL systems. This paper proposes a novel robust aggregation algorithm against poisoning attacks in a three-layer multi-stage FL system that consists of device, edge, and cloud layers. We evaluate the proposed robust algorithm considering an Augmented Reality (AR) application with different poisoner placements and attack strategies. The evaluation results show that the proposed algorithm can effectively defend against poisoning attacks in three-layer multi-stage FL systems.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Poisoning Attacks, Augmented Reality, Multi-stage FL

I. INTRODUCTION

Over the past years Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) techniques have become integral in a wide range of application areas, including healthcare, industry, education, Internet of Things (IoT), and autonomous driving [1]. As the applications become more distributed with many clients generating data in a distributed manner, distributed ML techniques like Federated Learning (FL) have emerged. FL is a collaborative and distributed ML technique that enables participants to train a common global model without sharing the raw data [2], already used in various applications. The raw data are retained by the distributed clients who generate the data, and only the locally trained model parameters are shared during the model training, thereby contributing to privacy preservation. The applicability of FL is well-studied for applications that require data privacy, including healthcare and autonomous driving [1].

A typical FL system comprises a set of distributed clients and a centralized server. FL is an iterative process that continues until convergence, i.e., all the clients have a properly trained model with them for inference. The server can be located in the cloud or in the edge environment, depending on the application requirements. The multi-stage hybrid FL introduced in [3] utilizes resources in the intermediate layers of the network architecture (ex: edge) between the

clients and the server to perform aggregations during FL training. These aggregations further reduce the data transfer toward the upper layers, thereby increasing link utilization efficiency. The multi-stage FL concept is used in cellular networks to improve communications [4] and in client-edge-cloud environments [5] to train models faster with better communication-computation trade-offs. The underlying 5G and 6G network infrastructure that facilitates the applications will potentially comprise device, edge, core, and cloud layers. Therefore, adapting multi-stage FL efficiently utilizes computing resources at each layer.

Despite the aforementioned benefits, FL is vulnerable to data and model poisoning attacks where an adversary manipulates a subset of clients participating in the federation and forces the model to learn inaccurately [6]. An adversary alters the training data in a data poisoning attack and manipulates the model parameters in a model poisoning attack. Poisoned models i.e., models trained toward a malicious objective, produce poor results at the inference stage. Therefore, poisoning attacks on distributed ML systems should be carefully considered, and possible defense mechanisms should be in place before their use in the applications.

Defenses against poisoning attacks, also called robust techniques, remove the poisoning effect on the aggregated model update. The state-of-the-art robust techniques against FL poisoning attacks consider a system with n distributed nodes and a single server [6]–[12]. These techniques are not tested by applying them in multi-stage FL scenarios. The limitations of existing defenses include; assuming that the majority of clients are benign [9], easily vulnerable to a higher number of poisoners (ex: Median [10]). Hence, there is a need to develop novel defense techniques that safeguard multi-stage FL systems from poisoning attacks.

We present a novel robust aggregation algorithm for multi-stage FL networks considering a three-layer AR application. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that examines the effects of poisoning attacks in multi-stage FL networks. This is also the first work that develops a robust algorithm against poisoning in multi-stage FL. It is designed without defining an upper bound for the percentage of poisoned AR devices in the system therefore, it performs efficiently in the presence of a higher number of poisoning clients. We conduct a wide range of experiments to show the

effectiveness of the novel algorithm. The proposed robust algorithm can be extended in various applications.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the related work on multi-stage FL systems, poisoning attacks, and existing robust techniques. Section III describes the use case, system architecture, and the limitations of existing robust techniques. Section IV presents the proposed novel robust aggregation algorithm and section V provides the systematic evaluation of the proposed algorithm. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper with the future research directions.

II. RELATED WORK

FL provides vital solutions in applications where a larger number of decentralized devices are associated with different services such as next-generation networked industrial systems [13], ultra-reliable low-latency vehicular communications [14]. Application of FL techniques in future wireless systems should not necessarily follow a star-based topology where a single server directly connects to multiple distributed nodes [15]. Multi-stage hybrid FL [3] proposes a method for a network-aware FL where the aggregation occurs at different layers of the network such as the fog and the cloud with the feasibility of peer-to-peer sharing of model updates.

Poisoning attacks on FL systems can be targeted poisoning attacks or untargeted poisoning attacks [16]. Another classification of poisoning attacks is data poisoning [16] and model poisoning [17]. Label flipping is a special case of data poisoning where the adversary changes the labels for chosen inputs before the local model training [18]. An adversary can also create a poisoned model update by directly manipulating the model parameters after training or creating a model update according to the attacking objective. In the above attacks, the poisoned FL models do not serve the requirements of the applications, but a malicious objective.

Robust algorithms defend FL models from poisoning attacks. Early defenses such as Krum [7] and Bulyan [8] operate based on Euclidean distance, and they are insufficient against modern sophisticated/coordinated attacks. FoolsGold [6] uses a clustering method based on the cosine similarity of the gradient updates. Trimmed mean [10] and Median [10] use different aggregation rules at the server rather than federated averaging. A recent algorithm FLAME [9] uses a generalized approach by combining clustering and differential privacy techniques but assumes that the benign node population in the FL system is $> 50\%$. All the above techniques consider a system with n distributed nodes and a single server.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM MODEL

A. Use Case

Augmented Reality (AR) technology provides an enhanced perception of real-world objects, by including additional information over the user's actual view [19]. In general, an AR system projects computer-generated augmentations on top of real objects, combining real and virtual objects to function synchronously. ML can be used in AR for various

tasks including object recognition, object tracking, movement prediction, and language translation [20] in different applications such as industry, education, medicine, and gaming. The applicability of FL is immense in learning tasks of AR due to FL's ability to learn from distributed data without sharing raw data, as AR devices typically generate a large amount of data. The use of cloud-based, edge-based, and hybrid architectures in AR leads to the effective utilization of resources available at different layers of the network [19]. Multi-stage FL architectures potentially have wide applicability in AR systems since they utilize abundant resources at the intermediate layers to perform aggregations. We propose our robust multi-stage FL solution for a distributed AR system as depicted in fig. 1.

B. System Architecture

We use a multi-stage AR network architecture comprising 3 layers (cloud, edge, and device) as our FL network. The layers are numbered from 0 to 2, where we denote the cloud layer as layer 0 and the AR device layer as layer 2. The device layer has 10 client networks with 250 AR devices in total, as shown in fig. 1. For simplicity, fig. 1 only shows the AR devices in two user layer networks. The AR devices are participating in an FL process to eventually obtain a trained model to solve a certain ML problem, for example, an image recognition problem. The cloud server coordinates the FL training process. We avoided choosing a highly symmetrical network architecture since it would be a special case. We also avoided choosing a highly asymmetric network architecture with a highly biased number of AR devices in the user layer networks. This is because the existing robust techniques may not be effective with user networks having a few AR devices at the user layer.

C. Effect of Poisoning

Poisoning attacks force the FL system to train inaccurately and serve a malicious objective of an adversary, for example, identifying an object incorrectly. Fig. 2 illustrates a potential targeted poisoning attack in an image recognition task of an AR system. The ML task of the AR device at the inference stage is to identify the letters and the digits of a given image. Let's assume the poisoning objective of the adversary is to manipulate the FL process such that the trained system is forced to identify the digit "1" as digit "7", but behave normally on all other letters and digits as depicted in fig. 2.

To demonstrate the poisoning effect and measure the decrease in the accuracy of prediction, we choose MNIST dataset and (source \rightarrow target) label flipping targeted data poisoning attack. We choose (1 \rightarrow 7) label flipping attack as chosen by literature [6], [21]. The attackers are assumed to be a set of compromised AR devices that performs the local training using flipped data. We use two performance measuring metrics to evaluate the FL system's performance during a poisoning attack. We use Main task Accuracy (MA) and Backdoor Accuracy (BA) at the test phase as the performance metrics following the recent literature [9]. MA indicates the accuracy of a model in its benign task, which is the fraction of correctly predicted outcomes to the benign inputs. The

Fig. 1: A multi-stage FL system with device, edge, and cloud layers for AR use case.

Fig. 2: Targeted poisoning in an image recognition problem.

adversary aims to minimize the effect on MA to remain undetected. BA indicates the accuracy of the backdoor task. It is the fraction of the trigger set for which the model provides the wrong outputs as chosen by the adversary. The adversary aims to maximize BA. An effective defense prevents the adversary from increasing BA. We report the average across 20 experiments in all cases, unless otherwise mentioned.

The baseline results for the experiments with no poisoning attack and no defense implemented are, MA = 84.45%, and BA = 0.026% as shown in fig. 3. Then we vary the attacker percentage from 10% to 80%, assign attackers randomly to the user networks, launch the label flipping attack, calculate MA and BA, and plot them in fig. 3. When the attacker percentage is 30% and onward, BA substantially increases, proving the attack is more successful when the attacker count is high.

D. Robust techniques against poisoning and limitations of existing defenses

Robust techniques/algorithms defend the FL system from poisoning attacks by filtering out the effect of the poisoners at the central server. The central server sends a benign model to the AR devices for the inference task. Fig. 4 illustrates how an AR device will perform the same task when a robust algorithm is in place to remove the poisoning effect. The model no longer predicts incorrectly as done in fig. 3.

Early defenses like Krum [7] needs an estimate of the number of poisoning users in the system, which is unrealistic

Fig. 3: Comparison of accuracy between non-poisoning and poisoning scenarios

Fig. 4: Removal of poisoning effect by robust techniques.

knowledge to have at the central server. Median [10] is effective until the poisoner percentage is 50% of the total client population. FLAME [9], SEAR [11], and LoMar [21] have an upper bound on the number of poisoners in the system. These solutions are ineffective when the poisoner count exceeds the upper bound. Moreover, none of these algorithms are tested for multi-stage FL networks. FoolsGold algorithm [6] does not define such an upper bound and is designed to defend a typical FL system with one server and n clients. FoolsGold is robust for a wide range of poisoner percentages however, it is also not tested for multi-stage FL networks. FoolsGold uses a detection logic based on behavior similarity. Therefore, it also fails with certain

attacker configurations such as fully poisoned networks at the user layer as depicted in fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Fraudster placement when one network is fully poisonous.

We empirically evaluate the performance of the FoolsGold for the proposed multi-stage FL network architecture and present the results in Table I. The high values for BA show that the FoolsGold is not an effective defense technique to defend the multi-stage FL network from poisoning attacks. MA does not deviate much from the benign scenario showing that the targeted poisoning attack does not affect the performance of other classes.

TABLE I: Performance metrics of FoolsGold under different poisoner configurations

Metric	Not Poisoned	One Network is Fully Network Poisoned
MA	84.45	81.10
BA	0.026	98.74

IV. NOVEL ROBUST TECHNIQUE FOR MULTI-STAGE FL

This section presents the defense objectives and design concepts for multi-stage robust FL. Moreover, the section explains the technical details of each step of the proposed novel robust algorithm.

A. Defense Objectives

A general defense against targeted FL poisoning should fulfill the following objectives. *Effectiveness, performance, and independence from data distributions and attack strategies* [9]. Effectiveness ensures that the defense removes the poisoning effect and achieves a non-poisoned model for inference as depicted in fig. 4. Performance ensures the benign performance of the FL process is preserved i.e., the defense does not degrade the performance of the original FL task. The defense should also be applicable to different data distributions and different attack strategies, and should not use prior information about the poisoning AR clients.

A defense algorithm applicable to multi-stage FL systems should fulfill the following additional design objectives. *Independent of poisoner distribution* i.e., networks at the AR device layer may have poisoned AR devices distributed in different ways and the defense should be robust against any poisoner distribution, including fully poisoned AR networks. In addition to that, a strong robust aggregation algorithm should also be *Robust in the presence of a varying number of poisonous AR devices (including 50% of total clients and more)*.

B. Design Concepts and Elements

1) **Dynamic Model Clustering:** At each edge server at layer 1, the robust algorithm must consider the weights of the updated local models received from its AR network and it must dynamically cluster the models in a network into multiple clusters. A poisoned model having a malicious objective wants to deviate the learning process from the benign objective. Therefore, it should possess different characteristics compared with the benign models. If there are multiple AR device groups with different poisoning objectives, the robust algorithm should cluster them into different clusters, and benign clients into a separate cluster. Since we cannot pre-define the number of clusters in advance, KMeans clustering algorithm which uses the number of clusters as an input parameter is not suitable for the task. Instead, we use a density-based clustering mechanism called HDBSCAN. Density-based clustering characterizes clusters as areas of high density separated from other clusters by areas of low density. HDBSCAN dynamically determines the number of clusters and its only input parameter is the minimum cluster size, which we set as 2. It also separates the outliers. The clustering should also happen at the central cloud server for the respective models received from the edge servers.

2) **Model Averaging:** Once a node (edge server or the central cloud server) performs HDBSCAN clustering for the model received from the lower layer, the cluster averages should be taken excluding the outliers. Edge servers must send all the cluster averages to the cloud server without filtering out any cluster averages. It makes sure that the cloud server receives sufficient averaged models from the edge layer, producing better clustering results at the cloud server.

3) **Filtering of Averaged Models:** The cloud server receives averaged models from layer 1. The cloud server should also perform clustering, outlier filtering, and cluster averaging same as the edge servers. In addition to that, the cloud server should pick the best possible cluster (a cluster that consists of model updates with benign characteristics) to continue with the next iteration of the learning, while discarding the other cluster averages. We may also encounter fully compromised AR networks at the layer 2. If an AR network is fully compromised, all the models of that network are likely to fall under one cluster at edge layer clustering, and the average of that cluster is also sent to the cloud server. Even though malicious model averages are propagated toward layer 0, the properties of the averaged malicious models show the properties of a poisoned model, and the robust algorithm must filter them at the cloud server. We evaluate two filtering mechanisms at the central server, i.e. based on cosine similarity and euclidean distance. Based on empirical results, we use euclidean distance based filtering which provided better results.

C. Novel Robust Algorithm

- **Step 1:** The cloud server at layer 0 sends the global model to all AR devices. If it is the beginning of the training (at $t = 0$), the cloud server creates the global

Fig. 6: Steps of the novel robust algorithm for three-layer multi-stage FL system.

model and sends it. For a given iteration t , the cloud server sends the previous iteration’s global model (the best cluster average from the previous iteration) to all the AR devices. The mechanism to select the best cluster is outlined in step 5.

- **Step 2:** Each AR device uses its local data and trains the received model from the cloud server. The produced model updates are transmitted to the respective edge server in layer 1 by the AR devices.
- **Step 3:** Each edge server collects the model updates received from its clients, apply the HDBSCAN clustering algorithm, and clusters the model updates into P clusters and a set of outliers. P is dynamically selected with the constraint of minimum cluster size = 2. Each edge server discards the outliers, calculate the per cluster average, and sends the per cluster averages to the cloud server at layer 0. The edge servers do not filter out any cluster average.
- **Step 4:** Each edge server transmits the per cluster average to the cloud server.
- **Step 5:** The cloud server collects all the averages received from layer 1 and applies HDBSCAN clustering algorithm to produce Q clusters and potentially a set of outliers. The cloud server then discards the outliers and performs cluster averaging. For each cluster, the cloud server calculates the euclidean distance between each cluster element and the previous global model and takes the average of the euclidean distance for each cluster. The cloud server then selects the cluster with minimum averaged euclidean distance as the “best cluster” and use its cluster average as the global model for $t = t + 1$.

Fig. 6 illustrates each step of the novel robust algorithm alongside the 3-layer multi-stage FL network.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

This section presents the performance evaluation results of the proposed defense mechanism for multiple scenarios using the MNIST dataset and shows that the robust algorithm satisfies the defense objectives outlined in section IV-A. We evaluate the algorithm against different poisoner placements and multiple poisoning attacks by compromised AR devices.

A. Performance against different poisoner placements

We use Independent and Identically Distributed (IID) data for these experiments. The baseline values are MA = 84.45% and BA = 0.026% where neither the attackers nor the defense algorithm is in the system. The system achieves nearly identical performance (MA = 85.76% and BA = 0.035%) with the robust algorithm implemented when there are no poisoning attacks, satisfying the design objective 2, *performance*.

1) *Random poisoner placement:* Fig. 7(a) and fig. 7(d) show the behavior of MA and BA respectively for the attack scenario with randomly placed poisoning AR devices. Fig. 7(d) shows how the system recovers to the baseline performance with the robust algorithm in place, satisfying the design objective 1, *effectiveness*, and design objective 5, *robustness in the presence of varying numbers of poisoners*.

2) *Biased and distributed poisoner placements:* The biased and distributed placements of poisoners are depicted in fig. 8. We define the biased poisoner placement as the scenario where there are one or few AR networks that are fully poisoned. In distributed poisoner placement, there is at least one poisoning AR device in each layer 2 network.

Fig. 7 also depicts the performance of the defense algorithm with biased and distributed poisoning AR device placements. Fig. 7(b) and fig. 7(c) show that the MA remains almost the same for both biased and distributed poisoner placements, revealing that the benign task performance is ensured irrespective of the poisoner placement. Fig. 7(e)

Fig. 7: Accuracy of the robust algorithm against the percentage of poisoning clients for random, biased, and distributed poisoner placements.

Fig. 8: Biased and distributed placement of the poisoners.

and fig. 7(f) show that BA gets severely affected by the increased number of poisoners but the defense algorithm recovers the system to the baseline BA values. Therefore, defense objective 4 (*independent of poisoner distribution*) is satisfied.

B. Robustness against multiple poisoning attacks

Fig. 9: Targeted multiple poisoning in an image recognition problem.

Poisoning attacks are not limited to single-label flipping attacks. As a different attacking strategy, the attacker may attempt multiple label flipping attacks to further harm the FL system while maintaining the stealthiness goal. A multiple poisoning attack performs more than one poisoning attack simultaneously as depicted in fig. 9. A sophisticated robust

algorithm should prevent the FL system from multiple poisoning attacks. We evaluate the performance of the novel robust algorithm against multiple poisoning attacks with an MNIST IID dataset. In addition to the (1 \rightarrow 7) label flipping, we execute (5 \rightarrow 8) label flipping also during our multiple poisoning attack on the AR system. The baseline values are MA = 87.63% and BA = 2.662% where neither the attackers nor the defense algorithm is in the system. MA and BA are different from the single poisoning attack scenario because the main task is now different. The system achieves nearly identical performance (MA = 87.34% and BA = 2.486%) with the robust algorithm implemented when there are no poisoning attacks, showing that the defense algorithm has no negative effects on the non-poisoned system.

Fig. 10 shows the behavior of MA and BA for the multiple poisoning attack scenario for random, biased, distributed poisoning AR device placements. Fig. 10(a), fig. 10(b), and fig. 10(c) shows that the effect on MA is minimal even in a multiple poisoning attack irrespective of the poisoner placement. Fig. 10(d), fig. 10(e), and fig. 10(f) show how the system recovers to the baseline performance with the robust algorithm in place. Therefore, the defense algorithm is effective against multiple poisoning attacks satisfying the defense objective 3, which is the *robustness against different attack strategies*.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The paper presented a novel robust aggregation algorithm against poisoning attacks in a three-layer multi-stage FL network consisting of device, edge, and cloud layers. Extensive evaluations conducted on the robust algorithm considering a multi-stage AR network revealed that the algorithm successfully defends against a wide range of poisoning attacks. The dynamic clustering allows the algorithm to be robust in the presence of multiple poisoning attacks and it is effective against different poisoning user placements such as random, biased, and distributed. The solution does not assume that the majority of the users are benign and the algorithm is even robust when 80% of the users are poisoners. The solution recovers the poisoned multi-stage FL network close to its

Fig. 10: Accuracy of the robust algorithm against the percentage of poisoning clients during a multiple poisoning attack.

baseline backdoor accuracy values which are 0.026% for single poisoning attacks and 2.662% for multiple poisoning attacks.

In future research, we will extend this work beyond a three-layer multi-stage FL network and produce a more generalized algorithm. We will also test the algorithm with non-IID data. We will apply the algorithm to different datasets in different applications to demonstrate the wide applicability of the algorithm.

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